

Grant Agreement Number: 723265

Project acronym: **Clusters 2.0**

Project full title: Clusters 2.0 - Open network of hyper connected logistics clusters towards Physical Internet

D.4.1

Specification sheet of designated NMLU

Due delivery date: 05/01/2018

Actual delivery date: 05/01/2018

Organization name of lead participant for this deliverable: Fraunhofer IML

Project co-funded by the European Commission within Horizon 2020		
Dissemination level		
PU	Public	x
PP	Restricted to other programme participants	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

Deliverable number:	D4.1
Deliverable responsible:	IML
Work package:	WP 4
Editor:	IML

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Document Revision History			
Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
V0.1	13.07.2017	Basic draft, table contents, structure	IML, MOSAIC
V0.2		Introduction section	Mines ParisTech
V0.3.1	26.07.2017	Content chapter 2 and 3	IML
V0.3.2	31.07.2017	Content chapter 4	VEG, IML
V0.4.1	22.09.2017	Content chapter 5	IML
V0.4.2	18.09.2017	Content chapter 6	IML, VEG
V0.5	17.10.2017	Review and remarks on specific contents	all
V0.6	20.10.2017	Review and remark	Innovatrain
V0.7	26.10.2017	Update Content chapter 5, 6	IML
V0.8	13.12.2017	Review and changes	all
V0.9	14.12.2017	Update all chapters	IML
V1.0	21.12.2017	Final Deliverable	IML
V1.0	22.12.2017	Final review	PTV

Abstract
Work package 4 analyzes, proposes, develops and prototypes New Modular Load Units (NMLUs) at a sub-container level. This document aims to set the starting point for that by determining logistical, functional, and technical requirements for a NMLU concept that has been developed and will be adjusted furthermore.

Note: This is a working document, which was evolving during the different stages of work in WP 4.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
Cross-docking	Logistics practice of unloading freight from an incoming mode of transport (semi-trailer, truck, wagon, etc.) and reloading it directly onto outgoing mode of transport (the same or different) with little or no storage between unloading and reloading. This is executed to change the type of transport, sort goods according to various destinations, or to combine goods from multiple origins to the same destination or route.
DC	Distribution Centre, Central Distribution
DIN	Deutsche Institut für Normung
EN	Europe Norm
FMCG	Fast-moving consumer goods. Retail goods that have a short shelf life and are sold quickly and at relatively low cost. Often commonly referred to as “groceries”.
FMCG industry / sector	Fast-moving consumer goods industry. Often commonly referred to as “the grocery industry”
GS1	A global organisation setting standards for the flow of information and goods, including identification, labelling and electronic commerce
Interconnection	The connecting separate networks through standards and protocols
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LL	Living Lab
LSP	Logistic Service Provider
Load carrier	Devices specifically designed for carrying and keeping goods together during transportation and handling. For example, loading pallet, roller container and milk cage.
MLU	Modular Unit Load
NB-IoT	NarrowBand IoT, is a Low Power Wide Area Network radio technology standard developed to enable a wide range of devices and services to be connected using cellular telecommunications bands
NMLU	New Modular Unit Load
PI	Physical Internet
POS	Point of Sale. The point at which the sale to the consumer is registered, for example, at a cash terminal or checkout
StVZO	Straßenverkehrs-Zulassungs-Ordnung, eng.: German Road Traffic Licensing Regulation
ULD	Universal Loading Device
WLAN	Wireless Local Area Network
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

Clusters 2.0s vision is to leverage the full potential of European Logistics Clusters for an efficient and fully integrated transport system in Europe and to demonstrate the scaling effects for the companies collaborating within logistics clusters. Within this context, work package 4 analyzes, proposes, develops and prototypes New Modular Load Units (NMLUs) at a sub-container level. This document aims to set the starting point for that by determining logistical, functional, and technical requirements for the NMLUs.

Starting from the FMCG point of view and keeping in mind the basis of reusable transport items formed by Modulushca boxes which was the outcome of the predecessor project, logistical parameters such as geometric dimensions and technical, mechanical, and physical properties were discussed within a close collaboration between the work package's project participants. As a result, three different NMLU concepts were identified that came out of the basic requirements and initial solutions that were captured before.

The discussion went on with additional requirements for the NMLUs that were arising from a holistic view on the supply chain, especially shipping from manufacturing plants to customer DCs/cityhubs including the last-mile aspect, which covers shipments from customer DCs/cityhubs to the stores/consumers. During workshop sessions, the work package partners involved in this task have come to identify the overall supply chain that covers the various use cases and their designated stakeholders and also requirements that were directly influencing the needs concerning the NMLU.

As the result of this, the so called Subframe concept has been chosen over the other two. The concept includes two main components with the NMLU being seen as an individual sub-container and the subframe (owned by shipper) as a so-called bottom module, which acts as a supporting ground frame for construction, complies with the standardized, minimally corresponding profile for guidance, rotating displacement and fixing options for the NMLUs, and which provides the possibility of handling forklift trucks on at least the short sides of the NMLUs.

As for now, the biggest benefits for using such a subframe system lie within the possibility of unloading sideways (City-Transport) and backwards (CD and DC) because of no need to load the NMLUs in prescribed sequence which makes the LiFo principle become obsolete. Furthermore, this leads to more technical possibilities for automated loading and unloading systems and generally, the handling effort within cross docking processes can be significantly reduced as NMLUs can be easily swapped between (various) means of transportation.

Besides the technical realization and prototyping of the NMLU solution, evaluating the use cases in respect of market share and types of products that may be beneficial for such a case will be the upcoming task. Once these are identified, proper business cases have to be evaluated in order to outline benefits for all the stakeholders of the overall supply chain involved.

1 Introduction

After several national projects that demonstrated the stakes, the EU Clusters 2.0 project are contributions toward the development and experimentation at an international level in the FMCG (Fast Moving Consumer Goods) sector. Their aim is to: demonstrate the stakes, propose a vision, create a toolbox for interconnectivity, assess transformation changes at IT and operational levels, do experimentations and validate the roadmap towards implementation of Physical Internet (PI) in the FMCG sector.

1.1 Project Clusters 2.0

Clusters 2.0's vision is to leverage the full potential of European Logistics Clusters for an efficient and fully integrated transport system in Europe and demonstrate the scaling effects for the companies collaborating within logistics clusters.

One of the biggest challenges of European transport system is establishing collaboration among logistics stakeholders to optimize transport operations at lowest environmental impact and to leverage additional scale effects to reduce costs. Clusters 2.0 will provide solutions from four development streams:

- Establish CargoStream an open Pan-European community approach of shippers to scale supply chain efficiency through bundling their regular transportation demand with other shippers and to favor intermodal alternatives.
- Develop New Modular Loading Units and innovative handling and transshipment technology to accelerate handling processes within clusters for road and intermodal modes.
- Implementing a first of a kind prototype on a Cluster Community System for standard message and information exchange and asset management within logistics clusters.
- Develop governance models introducing the role of a neutral agent that will form the basis for new collaborative business models building up on the work of the FP7 project CO3.

Clusters 2.0 will provide a toolbox for future logistics including large scale IT applications establishing and facilitating collaboration within and across logistics clusters. Compared to previous approaches Clusters 2.0 will advance by adding elements of horizontal collaboration, modularization and standardization of loading units to the concept of logistics clusters. Clusters 2.0 will increase the engagement, performance and coordination of terminals and hubs at cluster and network level targeting an increase by 50% of the freight managed within clusters intermodally.

1.2 Description of the starting point

Clusters 2.0 will analyse, propose, develop and prototype New Modular Load Unit (NMLU) at sub-container level. Considering above mentioned background, a critical question is to analyse if a unique type of NMLUs is appropriate for ISO container (or flat rack), European swapbodies and trailers. A NMLU compatible with CEN swapbodies, suitable for intra-European transport by road, rail and ferry boats will be analyzed.

NMLU will be suitable:

- for maximizing bundling opportunities and increased load factors in vehicles,
- for effective transshipment as described in C3,
- for last/first mile, maximizing the opportunity for smaller players to enter into the use of intermodal solutions and
- for big players to do smaller shipments to certain destination including shipments for city logistics.

NMLU will be complementary to current modular units providing flexibility to the intermodal system. The prototyped modular load units developed by VEG (www.vaneckgroup.com) will be used, tested and validated specifically in Living Lab 3 (LL 3) which is led by JDR (www.janderijk.com).

LL 3 acts at Cluster level to test and validate the New Modular Load Unit (NMLU) together with innovative handling and transshipment technology to accelerate handling processes within clusters for road and intermodal modes, into a real business context WP 4 outputs. LL 3 is constructed into 3 business related scenarios:

- Warehousing
- Intermodal transportation (truck and train)
- City distribution
- Collaboration

The NMLU will cover the existing gap between containers and pallets to provide flexibility and efficiency to the intermodal network and improving the links with city distribution.

Work Package 4 (WP 4) addresses the design of New Modular Load Units (NMLU) that can be used by the participating actors along the supply chain, in order to reach the previously named goals. The goal is to build a prototype that will be used in an application environment (Living Labs). Therefore, it is needed to define all the technical requirements within a specification sheet.

1.3 Modularization and standardization of loading units

Unit load groups primary and transport products to facilitate transport and handling. It is one of key cost drivers across the supply chain which facilitates transport, storage and handling of products. Generally, five levels can be outlined for current state of goods capsulation and unit load design. Firstly, the sales units are constituted in primary packaging that refers to the package to the final consumers. The conception of primary packaging is often subject to product design (dimensions, weight, fragility, and etc.) and marketing needs. Then secondary unit load or secondary packaging is used to combine primary units into basic handling units as to ease the handling, transportation as well as storage, such as trays, totes, crates or boxes. After the third level unit load palletizing secondary unit load or primary packaging on pallets, shrink-wrap, dollies, roll cages etc. The fourth encapsulation tier lies the shipping container, such as maritime containers. Finally, the fifth tier loads goods into carriers such as road based trucks, semi-trailers, delivery vans, scooters and bicycles, railcars, barges and ships, etc.

A challenge ahead for unit load design is the different solutions used by many stakeholders when assembling unit loads. That is, unit load is traditionally designed in its own silo, disconnected from the rest of the supply chain. This results in a wide variety of unit load dimensions and too many standards differing from country to country. Established international standards are not always used. Global inefficiencies arise by the diversity of packaging solutions:

- Poor fill levels of packing units and transportation means, e.g., averagely 42,6% utilization of trucks and containers at departure;
- Poor storage space utilization;
- Inefficiencies in handling, e.g., pack and repack of products among partners to feed into new systems;
- Higher chances of theft and bad influence of weather circumstances when products are temporally stored in the open;
- Difficulties to feed into new systems (automatic warehouses) and store formats, resulting in increasing costs and time to market;

- Negative environmental impacts, e.g., increasing waste, CO2 emission.

In face of challenges, modular unit load design has been demonstrated with the potential of driving supply chain efficiency through standardization. More broadly, modularization refers to making things fit from production line to shelves and making different logistic actors working together. The modularization project of Consumer Goods Forum concludes the following five main levers for modularization [1]:

- (1) Optimized handling and ergonomics for all supply chain stakeholders: Non-value added handling is reduced through modularization, with much less packing, re-packing and picking to feed into new systems among partners. Additionally, participants saw highly improved handling efficiency in automated systems, as well as improved handling efficiency at retail with adapted solutions going directly to shelves;
- (2) Maximized cube utilization within the box, handling unit and transportation means, due to the versatility of packing different products in same boxes, less void inside the box and more efficient stackability of modular boxes;
- (3) Efficient reverse logistics and less waste due to standardization of boxes.
- (4) Enhanced service through reduced lead times and improved shelf availability;
- (5) Improved quality, with reduced damage in automated handling systems.

1.4 Goods travel in interconnect logistic networks

The concept of PI (Physical Internet) arose from the metaphor of Digital Internet. In Digital Internet, the data of messages and addresses are embedded in digital data packets through standardized universal codes and protocols. With all the information in the digital data packet as well as the protocols in Internet servers and routers, the digital data packet routes automatically and independently of infrastructure among the interconnected servers / routers in the Internet until it reaches its destination.

Inspired by this metaphor, the Physical Internet intends to do it similarly with goods having to flow through it. In other words, just like data packets and servers in Digital Internet, the goods in the PI are encapsulated in standard modular PI containers that route among PI hubs and that are to be the material-equivalent to data packets. The PI containers aim to encapsulate and protect goods in open interconnected logistics networks. PI containers from different logistics actors are transported by numbers of certified transportation and logistics service providers across multiple mode. They are also to be handled and stored in numerous certified open logistics facilities, notably for consolidated transshipment and distributed deployment across territories. They are to be used from production line all the way to retail stores and homes. By this way, all users including suppliers, shippers, retailers, and consignees can share this same logistic system, which enables full horizontal and vertical coordination in logistics networks and drives supply chain efficiencies.

2 WP 4 - New Modular Load Units (NMLU) and Automatized Transshipment

This deliverable deals with one specific task of the Clusters 2.0 project: WP 4.1 - Specification sheet of designated NMLU. In this chapter following parts will be introduced:

- Overall objectives of the Work package 4 (WP 4)
- A resume of what was done and decided in task 4.1
- Description of the different tasks in task 4.1
- Organization of the document
- Division of work in task 4.1

2.1 Overall Objectives WP 4

WP 4 aims to develop low cost, low capital and investment intensive enhanced goods handling and transshipment solutions. WP 4 will:

- Develop prototypes of New Modular Load Units.
- Develop low cost, low capital and investment intensive enhanced goods handling and transshipment solutions.
- Develop advanced logistics services for integrated manufacturing.

WP 4 is directly linked to WP 5 – LL 3 providing requirements, implementing and testing the NMLU and handling and transshipment technology and transferring the concept to other clusters within and outside Clusters 2.0 scope.

2.2 Objectives Task 4.1

In the first step logistical, functional and technical requirements for the NMLU (New Modular Load Unit) will be determined. Therefore, a defined case (at the moment FMCG) will be analyzed and restrictions within a supply chain worked out. These includes logistical parameters, as geometric dimensions and technical/mechanical/physical properties based on handling systems, used materials handling components and storage and stacking systems. Additionally, the requirements for static and dynamic loads and climatic conditions will be derived from the respective distribution chain. Technical requirements relating to labelling, AutoID systems and integrated cooling and safety systems are also added.

Interviews among the project participants provide a first information basis. Based on the gained knowledge a requirement profile will be designed. For any further consideration, some on site visits will be made. Through prioritizing, clustering and evaluating the different requirements and restrictions will finally provide “must have” and “nice to have” criteria of the NMLU.

The conception of the NMLU is based on the clustered results of the requirements analysis as well as available packaging and container systems. At the beginning a market research will be executed, that shows up the advantages and disadvantages of e.g. available heavy load carrier systems.

In Chapter 6 the NMLU concept is briefly outlined, including the prioritized conditions. After that the participants will value the conceptions based on technical feasibility, degree of fulfilment of the demands and the possibility of automation.

The result of the conception will be at least one or more NMLU concept versions, which will be prototypically implemented in the next step.

2.3 Organization of the document

After the first introduction and general description of the work in WP 4 the following chapters will deal with the different tasks carried out in the task 4.1:

Clusters 2.0

- NMLU related sub-container concepts (see chapter 3)
- Requirements from a logistics perspective (see chapter 4)
- Use case approach for NMLU (see chapter 0)
- NMLU Design concepts (see chapter 6)

In particular, chapters 4 and 5, have been identified via a survey (see Annex 8) at the beginning of the work package which led to the recording of the different requirements placed on a new sub-container. The anonymized survey ensured that each partner (whether it was a manufacturer, shipper, logistic service provider or carrier) had the opportunity to register the restrictions for the NMLU from its context as well as the status quo desired requirements for the future NMLU.

2.4 Division of work in task 4.1

In order to reach the objectives that are described above, the different competencies of the partners involved can be found in Table 1.

Table 1 - Devision of work

Partner	Task and competences
IML	task leader and manage process for specification and development, including solution principles for the NMLU concepts
JDR	responsible for the LL 3 and design of business related test scenarios for NMLU and simultaneous design of NMLU in WP 4 from LL 3 persepective
VEG	responsible for the functional requirements survey for transport interfaces and development of solution ideas to NMLU concepts and also for building the NMLU prototypes
PGBS, EQUIMODAL, INNOVATRIN AND CITYDEPOT	responsible for the functional design requirements out of use case perspective
UA	responsible for the general design requirements out of state of the art perspective
Mines ParisTech	responsible for functional requirements from modularization point of view

3 NMLU related previous sub-container concepts

From the sub-container perspective, there have been and are currently different concepts available, which are implemented or are during application phase or even have failed already. The relationship with the NMLU can be seen so far, that the upcoming systems listed below have the initial idea of a sub-container and have been designed either for rail traffic or the inner city distribution. The following overview shows NMLU related concepts which on the one hand can provide best practice approaches for the implementation and rapid acceptance among the stakeholders and on the other hand it can be seen why some of them have failed.

Table 2: Overview to NMLU related concepts

“Wechselbehälter mit Energiespeicher” (2011) Germany		Status
<p>Fail factors: Working in progress</p>		
“STADSBOX - City Box” (2005) Netherlands		Status
<p>Fail factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of supportive policies by Dutch municipalities - Critical mass is needed for participation - No direct success on national scale - Lack of quality in the process management are related to financial structures and conditions (e.g. budgets) - Lack of a strong project manager - Problems and challenges in the innovation project - Project was focused on an immediate national-wide introduction (rather than first starting to demonstrate the value of such a load unit in small-scaled pilots) - Commitment among retailers for the intended large-scale introduction was too limited - A large retailer that initially was a driving force in the project got increasingly convinced that introduction of the CityBox could well undermine its own strong position in the retail market → retailer withdrew its support 		
“i.log City Logistics” (2004) Italy		Status

<p>Fail factors: Unknown</p>		

<p>“PX Container” (2001) South Africa</p>		<p>Status</p>
<p>Fail factors: Unknown</p>		

<p>“Idioma - Combibox” (1999)</p>		<p>Status</p>
<p>Fail factors: The project was considered a demonstration project with a term of 30 months, possibly no use case</p>		

<p>“Hellmann Playbox” (1996) Germany</p>		<p>Status</p>
<p>Fail factors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of quality in the process management are related to financial structures and conditions (e.g. budgets) - Lack of strong project management Problems and unsolved challenges within innovation process</p>		

“CARGO 2000 Logistik Box” (1990) Germany		Status
Fail factors: Unknown, possibly lack of user/compatibilities		

“Laadkistvervoer per spoor / Von Haus zu Haus” (1939) Netherlands		Status
Fail factors: At the end of the Second World War, the concept was no longer needed and discontinued		

Reasons for failure

- High level of investment costs (funding problems)
- False distribution of costs (No cost-effectiveness of the project)
- Poor cost-benefit ratio (High manufacturing costs of sub-containers versus low savings with sub-container in use)
- Underestimation of influence of stakeholders in the transport chain as well as identifying those
- Sufficiently long period of testing, no testing in real logistics processes
- Not achieve a minimum required scale of operation
- Underestimation of governments influence (e.g. restrictions)
- Less need for action for changing external conditions (Progressing globalization and urbanization; growing volume of traffic in metropolitan areas)
- Weak project management and communication
- Lack of cooperation between project partners
- End of government funding or end of research project
- No business case or use case perspective for sub-container
- No product development and no market entrance strategy

The last column “Status” of the chart points out, if each single solution is still in use or not. A red colored light means that the concept has simply failed. A yellow colored light implies that a concept is still in its implementation phase. If the light is green the concept has become a solution and is in use.

The reasons for the failure of the above mentioned systems are mainly due to passing of sector needs (no business cases), the lack of standardization and of political support. The systems require new challenges – especially in the rail sector – such as high handling requirements, train and route utilization, and high investment requirements. The restriction of the financial structures and conditions often led to a weakening of the quality of the process management as well as problems and challenges during the innovation project. Since many parameters were to be taken into account, such as the quantity of mail or reception, the location of the railways connections (strong or weak rail connections) or the arrival time distribution. This was followed by the lack of strong and consistent project managers who pushed the project forward. In addition, the innovative transport systems required great effort such as detailed technical inspections, proof of the functionality of the system components within the framework of pilot plants and investment requirements, which many companies were rather skeptical about. Often, finding project support and participants in the pilot project has become a difficult task. The feasibility of all transport systems was present, but the implementation took too much time, which led to denial at national level.

Looking at the sector and at other (some failed) initiatives, the concept of Clusters 2.0 NMLU's should comply with several basic boundaries. These boundaries should be considered before evaluation and selection of the final NMLU concept:

- NMLUs should comply with the transport requirements of a specific transport segment. Here a distinction should be made between: hinterland/land transport, deep-sea or short-sea. For example, the regulation on the community, the maximum authorized dimensions in national and international traffic and the maximum authorized weights in international traffic:
<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A31996L0053>
- NMLUs should be in line with the dimensions of containers: hinterland/land transport (gives preference for 45 foot containers), deep-sea (gives preference to 20 or 40 foot containers) or short-sea (gives preference to 45 foot containers). The introduction of container has shaped all the equipment used for loading/transport/unloading units, hence the introduction of new loading units should not require further changes.
- NMLUs should take into account the market shift to an order supply chain. Under this context smaller and modular loading units should be possible to combine together in a loading unit. It will only reach high performance through standardization and modularization.
- NMLUs should take into account the problems with regard to reverse logistics and storage of empty units.
- NMLUs should be considered the same level as pallets (though, NMLUs are to fit more than 2 euro pallets in size for the transition phase). Consumer goods could then be packed on the production line and are no longer handled individually until delivered to the end customer or Hub.

4 Requirements from a logistics perspective

This chapter highlights the relevant requirements of load carriers regarding transportation, handling and storage. Those requirements are especially relevant for the development of a load carrier which is based on a standardized container. In a first step, all relevant interfaces in the various logistical processes are identified. According to the identified interfaces, requirements will be derived. All requirements and optional features which generate additional benefits of the NMLU are then assessed and grouped into must-have and nice-to-have criteria.

4.1 NMLU related Interfaces

In this chapter, the transshipment units are evaluated in regard to the various modes of transport. Due to different layouts of the transport vehicles it has to be assessed which size the transshipment unit can have. Also, it is important to highlight if existing handling equipment is usable for handling the transshipment unit.

Table 3 - Overview of NMLU related Interfaces

from	exchange	to	Transshipment unit	Handling Equipment	Usability of NMLU

The table one can see above points out which transshipment units can be used in the specific handling scenario. If for example the cargo needs to be transferred from vessel to train the transshipment unit would be an ISO-container. To execute this handling a reach stacker, gantry crane or rubber mounted gantry crane can be used.

The last column of the chart points out how the NMLU can be handled. A red colored box means that the NMLU cannot be used within this transshipment process. A yellow colored box implies that the NMLU can be handled if it is treated as a container. If the box is colored green the NMLU can be handled as single device.

4.2 NMLU related goods to be stored

NMLU must be designed for different load carriers and possible combinations of different units of the FMCG industry. The basis is formed by Modulushca boxes, because these boxes were designed for the FMCG industry in the predecessor project [2]. Also standardized reusable transport boxes for the FMCG industry for delivering to the point of sales were developed from GS1 Germany, FMCG manufactures and retailers [3].

An extended overview of all common load carriers, which are used in FMCG sector, see Annexes Table 10.

Figure 1 - Standardized Transportbox for FMCG Sector (1) Modulushca boxes (2) GS1 Transportbox [2], [3]

Within the FMCG sector pallet heights are based on the widely accepted EUL-recommendation. Therefore, the EUL-recommendation should be taken into consideration when planning respectively designing the NMLU. Not just the pallets comply with the EUL-recommendation but also the crates, see Annex table 11, will stack up to the same pallet heights that are defined in the recommendation, see Figure 2 [4], [5]:

Figure 2 - EUL-recommendation for pallet heights on Transportation and Warehousing (in accordance with [4])

Other dimensions are common for various units are common load carriers in the logistics to facilitate the transition from common system to the new system. The appearances (load carriers) can be divided into seven groups:

- Euro pallets
- UK pallets
- Rolling containers
- Trolleys
- Hanging transport clothes
- Loose packages
- Extraordinary goods (but falling within the size of the NMLU)

4.3 General requirements

In chapter 4.3 all general restrictions from logistics point of view will finally distinguish in must have and nice to have criteria of the NMLU.

Must-haves

The must-have criteria of the NMLU are identified aspects of a container based NMLU. These must be fulfilled in order for the NMLU to have a realistic chance to become a replacement or competitor of the traditional container. The criteria are listed in the following table.

Table 4 – Codification of must-have requirements

Code	Descriptions of the requirements
RM-1	economically competitive
RM-2	better in accessibility, traffic safety and the environment in the Urban areas
RM-3	lightweight: tara weight of the NMLU must be minimal
RM-4	resistant to the reaction forces of the vehicle and the walls must be strong enough for the load masses
RM-5	resistant to various (extreme) weather conditions: sealed
RM-6	safe against vandalism

RM-7	maintenance free
RM-8	tilt-proof
RM-9	stable in an operating environment of -20°C bis +30°C and four climate zones [6]
RM-10	capable in the humidity up to 80 % (max.) [6]
RM-11	must not be affected by UV light
RM-12	resistant to attack by common industrial and household chemicals
RM-13	resistant to absorbing moisture
RM-14	keep a high perceived quality throughout the product life
RM-15	provided with at least one door
RM-16	designed for automatic loading and unloading systems
RM-17	designed taking into consideration ergonomic aspects
RM-18	designed to secure the load, even partial load

Nice-to-haves

The nice-to-have criteria listed in Table 5 are features which separate the NMLU from traditional containers and offer additional benefits within the supply chain.

Table 5 – Codification of nice-to-have requirements

Code	Descriptions of the requirements
RN-1	loading different loading units / temperature groups together
RN-2	handling with common loading equipment into trailer or container, e.g. forklift, pallet truck (electric)
RN-3	communication for the Internet of Things (NB-IoT, mobile networks, BLE, WLAN)
RN-4	traceability
RN-5	checkability in exchange
RN-6	burglar-proof
RN-7	combined transport of different temperature groups in one NMLU (food industry)
RN-8	quiet loading and unloading (city night delivery)
RN-9	stackability
RN-10	folding
RN-11	stable in an operating environment of -40°C bis +60°C [6]
RN-12	capable of operating correctly in the humidity range 10 % to 80 % [6]

4.4 Bottom and Body

Apart from the general Must-have criteria there are specific requirements for individual parts of the NMLU. Within this chapter the requirements of the Bottom and body structure are outlined in following tables.

Table 6 – Requirements for NMLU Bottom

Code	Descriptions of the requirements
BM-1	must withstand any (impact) damage
BM-2	must be minimal in height
BM-3	must be suitable for transport via rolling devices for horizontal transport and other mobile transport material such as forklifts, thus being able to withstand a load due to lifting
BM-4	should be standardized for the fastening system to be used, which must be suitable for safe locking on a truck subframe and vehicle chassis
BM-5	should fit general cargo lock systems
BM-5.1	The construction of the bottom module must be in accordance with the "minimum corresponding bottom profile" flat surface. The bottom of the bottom module should be constructed such that all the time, stable movement over the rollers is possible.
BM-5.2	The structure of the "floor planes" of the bottom module must provide sufficient resistance to impression by the supporting rollers, to prevent damage and to obtain a low friction of the NMLU on the rollers. This should take into account higher dynamic loads due to the fact that the NMLU rests on the bullets during transport or retract rollers during transport
BM-6	4-way underpassability [7]: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - entry width long side > 710* mm - entry width short side > 580* mm - entry height > 95* mm - minimum space between entry slot > 228 mm
BM-7	high friction between the load and load surface and between the load units (sheet transport) must be ensured $\mu \geq 0,3$
BM-8	slip resistance on the forks of the forklift

Table 7 – Requirements for NMLU Body

Code	Descriptions of the requirements
BM-1	fixing – no restrictions
BM-2	at least two side access openings
BM-3	stacking pressure resistance should be guaranteed exclusively with the body, no additional reinforcements inside
BM-4	without risk of injury, no sharp or rough edges
BM-5	should include recyclable materials
BM-6	lightweight
BM-7	robust, weatherproof
BM-8	self-supporting, acts as a supporting ground frame for construction
BM-9	complies with the standardized, minimally corresponding profile for guidance, rotating displacement and fixing options
BM-10	weight wall need to withstand
BM-11	prepared for identification and tracking & tracing, no shielding of incoming and outgoing signals
BM-12	required maximum payload: 4.000 kg

4.5 Loading and Unloading in NMLU

To be a competitive load carrier the handling of the NMLU has to be doable with existing equipment. As the NMLU competes not just with a container but also with much smaller transport units the requirements listed in Table 8 regarding the handling are high.

Table 8 – Loading and Unloading requirements

Code	Descriptions of the requirements
LU-1	suitable for automated loading system for modulushca boxes (future)
LU-2	suitable for common transport equipment to load in NMLU
LU-2.1	How to get load carriers in: Drive in with pallet truck (electro) / rolcontainer / by hand
LU-2.2	How to secure the load carriers, how secure when not fully loaded. Attached load fuse fasteners must be sufficiently flexible and universal to ensure the different load carriers. This concerns at least rolling containers, hanging clothes and packages for packages
LU-3	designed for pre- loading a NMLU (in the absence of a vehicle / driver) in a DC must be possible
LU-4	suitable for automated and manual unloading

4.6 Transport and transshipment

During the transport and the transshipment of the NMLU the handling has to be as easy as possible. On the other side the NMLU has to be a safe load carrier. The requirements to fulfill these aspects are listed in the table below:

Table 9 – Transport and Transshipment requirements

Code	Descriptions of the requirements
TT-1	Transfer / shipment of the NMLU must be possible without opening the NMLU's
TT-2	The transshipment should preferably take place horizontally (by means of rows on / in the vehicles)
TT-3	The transport and transshipment systems should be specified in accordance with the NMLU Standard and preferably mechanized / automated Systems
TT-4	The transshipment systems must be user-friendly and with minimum maintenance
TT-5	Various contaminants of the roller devices should not adversely affect the operation
TT-6	Transport and transshipment systems must be suitable for handling a fully loaded NMLU and have sufficient reserve in case of overload
TT-7	Transport and transshipment systems must enable cooperation / outsourcing between carriers
TT-8	The effects of weight gain due to wheel alignment on the vehicle must have minimal impact on the load capacity
TT-9	NMLU vehicles must allow transport at the maximum permitted dimensions
TT-10	City distribution vehicles must fit within the city's acceptance and infrastructure

4.7 Requirements from a Supply Chain perspective

Chapter 4.7 collects all requirements related to NMLU from the holistic view on supply chain, especially to ship from manufacturing plants to customer DCs / cityhubs and also indeed the last-mile aspect, which covers shipments from customer DCs / cityhubs to the stores / consumers. For FCGM Supply Chain is characterized by different, almost opposite needs and requirements between at the beginning (manufacturer) and end of Supply Chain (city distribution).

4.7.1 Manufacturer

For a complete picture of the requirements of the NMLUs the whole supply chain needs to be taken into account. From the production of the raw materials up to the point of sale each step of the supply chain needs to be evaluated.

From a shipper point of view common transport loads are in format, which can accommodate both Euro Pallet and UK Pallet footprints. These pallets are common today in the Consumer Goods industry. The footprints are as follows:

- Euro pallet: 0.8 m x 1.2 m
- UK Pallet: 1.0 m x 1.2 m

The height does not exceed 2.55 m, so the manufacturer wants to double stack 2 pallets of 1.2 m height for optimal volume utilization in Trailer or 45 feet container. The major amount of transport flows is organized as a homogeneous handling units in full loads on trailer or container.

The flow is as follows, starting from the consumer:

- Level 0: Consumer either goes to the store to buy or pick up goods
- Level 1: Store gets delivered by a Cityhub (based on store orders)
OR
Store gets delivered by the DC of the retail chain (based on store orders).
- Level 2: Cityhub gets supplied by Manufacturer DC OR Cityhub gets supplied by Manufacturer Production Plant
- DC of the retail chain gets supplied by Manufacturer DC (based on retailer orders). OR
DC of the retail chain gets supplied by Manufacturer Production Plant (based on retailer orders).
- Level 3: Manufacturer DC gets supplied by Manufacturer Production Plant (based on a mix of forecast and orders).

According to GS1, optimization potentials during transport results when the products are packed onto EUL 1 or EUL 2. This reduces the number of pallets that are actually transported. Compared to the actual state, a simulation of different scenarios results in savings in fuel consumption and thus in CO₂ emissions of 8% average [5].

The saving effects at the level of the handling processes, e.g. in the goods receipt, stock transfer, picking, and goods out area are due to the adaptation of the EUL loading heights. In the pilot study, savings effects in trade and industry of up to 15% could be determined in relation to the processes under consideration. An actual end-to-end consideration of the chain is crucial [5].

From the point of the manufacturer the NMLU needs to fulfil the following aspects:

- NMLU should have the same height as the standard 45' intermodal container. This standard 45' intermodal container is used throughout Europe and is as far as all big FMCG players consider the standard. In general, NMLU height must be adapted to EUL-recommendations

- NMLU footprint should be designed for Euro pallets and UK pallets, also for future small footprints, like Modular Boxes (Modulushca)

4.7.2 City distribution

The ongoing trend towards urbanization results in more and more people that come and live in the cities. They are exposed to noise and particulate pollution as well as to CO₂ emissions, which is primarily caused by traffic. In addition, logistics and transport impact in the use of space within the cities and thus lead to urban conflicts.

The traffic interbranch forecast 2030 of the Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure predicts that the transport performance on the road will increase by almost 40% between 2010 and 2030. As a prediction, this means that the infrastructure will not be able to grow as fast as the actual need for traffic if urban logistics will stay in its current state.

Because of the increasing number of traffic jams caused by the previously described situation, there are high costs occurring every day. It is assumed that commuters and even craftsmen spend one full working day in traffic jam per month, which is caused by the low average speed of around 8 km per hour [8]. This example makes clear that there is a need for change which can be accomplished by the use of technology that is already available and even by making use of existing structures and processes.

The idea of a NMLU as a load carrier in a total solution for a sustainable distribution of goods to the inner city and back, fits into this context and targets making use of the existing infrastructure as a basis but at the same time changes the way things are done today by the restrictions of the commodities and resident law.

The goal of this case is to concretely define how the NMLU can function as an independent “micro hub” incorporated in activities of urban distribution to optimize the flow of goods. Minimal flow of goods and maximum efficiency of treatment for the flow of goods are the main target.

Originally, the concept of a micro hub is described as a small hub that may be a container, or any other type of stock unit (could also be the back area of a store) that is located in and around the city. Once filled with goods and/or parcels in the mornings, logistics service providers can use these hubs to pick up and deliver designated goods to the recipients. These containers may also be swap bodies that – instead of being delivered in the mornings – are loaded at the distribution center (DC) and then placed at their destination.

Within the case of the NMLU, a small-volume interchangeable mobile swap body is used as a unit in a 1:1 exchange for the retailers, meaning that one full NMLU is being delivered to the store, while the empty one – respectively filled with empties – is picked up and transported back to the DC.

Such a system comes with the following advantages:

- It circumvents restrictions on inner city delivery such as possible city entry restrictions for Diesel trucks and/or general denials for the inner city
- Using electric vehicles and low noise handling equipment enables night time deliveries [9]
- Delivery traffic can be shifted into the less stressed daytime and nighttime and thus offers corresponding solutions for these challenges
- The expansion of the delivery time windows into the night hours caused by low noise e-trucks also has the advantage that the vehicle fleet can be better utilized and thus fewer vehicles are needed for delivery
- In addition, participants are fulfilling their social responsibility by reducing climate-relevant emissions and noise pollution in urban areas

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- It satisfies the increasing demands from customers and end users, which expect an ever higher level of product freshness and product availability through the decoupling of market and delivery processes that enable efficiency and predictability of the presentation of goods throughout the day

Besides the advantages for such a system, the development of the NMLU focusing on city logistics has also been carried out on the analysis of cremated data and performance indicators for different branches in the field of delivery [2] [3]. In order to create the optimum conditions for bundling, the following requirements for the NMLU can be summarized:

- On average, 75-80% of the delivery volume per store is based on euro pallets, whereas the optimum quantity for bundling lies at an average of 4-6 euro pallets per branch
- For the 1:1 exchange of the swap bodies there needs to be special handling technology for the NMLU at the vehicle and/or store, and DC
- The length of the NMLU should be selected so that several cells can be loaded one after the other according to the system dimension on a semi-trailer
- The width of the cell shall be based on the width of air-conditioned vehicles according to § 32 StVZO

4.8 Environment and safety

The main objective of the D4.1 is to collect relevant requirements which the sub-container i.e. the NMLU needs to fulfil. These requirements are the foundation on which the design of the NMLU will be based. The main objective is to identify technical requirements that have an impact on the environment and safety such as payload, range, energy consumption, sustainability and economic feasibility when using the NMLU.

Apart of the CO₂ savings through better truck or train utilization, the use of NMLU should also implement a new eco friendliness to the SC system. This means waste savings through reduction in using cardboard and building the sub-container out of an environmental sustainable material. This topic of the eco friendliness of the NMLU will be part of task 4.3 and first possible solutions will be presented in D4.2.

NMLUs should be made of environment friendly materials, with minimal carbon footprint. This is crucial for the deployment of the NMLUs. However, in a project environment with budget constraints, there is no priority for the prototypes to be made of such materials. The choice of material will be made according to the needs of the prototype.

Another important aspect of the NMLU is the way the loaded goods are secured within the NMLU. As securing of freight is a time consuming manual task the NMLU shall be designed in a way that renders securing the freight unnecessary. This will be achieved by a form fit and optimized filling levels.

5 Development of NMLU use cases

Chapter 5 collects all requirements related to NMLUs from a holistic view on the supply chain, especially shipping from manufacturing plants to customer DCs/cityhubs including the last-mile aspect, which covers shipments from customer DCs/cityhubs to the stores/consumers. During WP4 workshop sessions, Clusters 2.0 partners involved in this task have come to identify the overall supply chain in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** that covers the various use cases and their designated stakeholders.

Figure 3 - Identified Overall Use Cases

The overall supply chain shows all the identified possible ways and connections between the different stakeholders from production site until the end customer. In order to make it more accessible, three different use cases can individually be looked at. These will be described in the following paragraphs. Each use case will be divided into the parts of the associated stakeholders in order to outline the changes that result from the NMLUs and the expected results on a qualitative basis.

5.1 Use Case 1 – Manufacturer Outbound directly to Store

Use case 1 aims to reduce handling effort for intermodal shifts and Cross Dock to a bare minimum, as NMLUs will not be opened until their end destination which will – in that case – be a larger type of store (possibly even malls) such as hypermarkets.

Figure 4 - Use Case 1: Manufacturer Outbound

5.1.1 Manufacturers/Producers

Instead of placing one product type onto one pallet, products will directly be loaded inside NMLUs. Possibly, direct orders (from e.g. hypermarkets) could be individually loaded into

NMLUs according to the order (e.g. half shampoo and half washing powder) and then directly be moved towards the outbound area.

Storing areas at the manufacturer site (or at manufactured DC) are currently being filled with products on pallets which in this case will change to NMLUs (at least for the type of products that will be shipped within NMLUs). In this use case, and if not directly ordered from the store, the NMLUs will also serve as the minimum picking quantity. Once an order has been made, the NMLUs will be sent to the upcoming Cross Docking Centre.

5.1.2 Cross Docking Centers

The Cross Docking Centre can be either owned by the manufacturer or other members of a common collaboration model or can be operated by a third party logistics provider. As pictured in Figure 5, the idea is that NMLUs that come from one manufacturing site (or another competitor within collaboration model) like A or B will be mixed together in order to form new combination of NMLUs like (1) or (2) for a truck (also works for trains). Within this use case, NMLUs will not be opened which will reduce the handling effort drastically.

Figure 5 - Cross Docking between NMLUs

5.1.3 End Destinations

For such a use case, only very large stores (possibly malls) may work as the final customer as they are able to inbound larger numbers of products of the same type (respectively, if order picked, a combination of products from one manufacturer). At this point of the supply chain, the NMLUs are opened for the first time and unloaded at the store. The transport vehicle will then pick up empty NMLUs that are – in the best case – filled with reusables and disposal.

5.2 Use Case 2 – Handling through Retailer DC

The second use case leaves the NMLUs unopened until they arrive at the Retailers DC (see Figure 6). From there on, products can be handled just like they are today or can be put into NMLUs for final distribution to stores. Either way, large sized stores or regular/smaller sized stores can be delivered.

Figure 6 - Use Case 2: Retailer DC

5.2.1 Manufacturers/Producers

Processes run analogical to chapter 5.1.1: Instead of placing one product type onto one pallet, products will directly be loaded inside NMLUs. Possibly, direct orders (from e.g. hypermarkets) could be individually loaded into NMLUs according to the order (e.g. half shampoo and half washing powder) and then directly be moved towards the outbound area.

Storing areas at the manufacturer site (or at manufacturer DC) are currently being filled with products on pallets which in this case will change to NMLUs (at least for the type of products that will be shipped within NMLUs). In this use case, and if not directly ordered from the store, the NMLUs will also serve as the minimum picking quantity until the retailer's DC. Once an order has been made, the NMLUs will be sent to the upcoming Cross Docking Centre.

5.2.2 Cross Docking Centers/Retailer DC

The Cross Docking Centre can be either owned by the manufacturer or other members of a common collaboration model or be operated by a third party logistics provider. As pictured in Figure 7, the idea is that NMLUs that come from one manufacturing site (or another competitor within collaboration model) like A or B will be mixed together in order to form new combination of NMLUs like (1) or (2) for a truck (also works for trains). Within this use case, NMLUs will not be opened which will reduce the handling effort drastically.

They are then sent to common Retailer DCs. The NMLUs will come inbound and unloaded for products to be either stored or picked for final distribution to the retailer's stores (business as usual – filling pallets or dollies with products). Instead of picking and loading transport vehicles for the milk run, NMLUs can be picked for store-wise distribution.

Figure 7 - Cross Dock at Retailer's DC

5.2.3 End Destinations

For such a use case, large stores (and possibly malls) and regular to smaller sized stores will work for final distribution either way. In the case that NMLUs are used for final distribution to

stores, the transport vehicle will pick up empty NMLUs that are – in the best case – filled with reusables and disposal.

5.3 Use Case 3 – 3rd Party Urban Hub

Use case 3 combines the functions of Cross Docking and the Retailer’s DC into one central Urban Hub at the edge of the cities. NMLUs will not be opened until they get there and are then picked (for regular transport vehicles or NMLUs just like in Use Case 2) for final distribution to larger/regular/smaller sized stores. For further business case consideration, it should be kept in mind that an Urban Hub could just as well be operated by a manufacturer/retailer within a collaboration model.

As another possible way of distribution, the NMLUs may function as a Micro Hub. Instead of being placed within the cities at different locations each, multiple ones that are set onto a subframe (see chapter 6.3) can be placed at one location for further distribution by e.g. cargo cruisers.

Figure 8 - Use Case 3: 3rd Party Urban Hub

5.3.1 Manufacturers/Producers

Processes run analogical to chapter 5.1.1: Instead of placing one product type onto one pallet, products will directly be loaded inside NMLUs. Possibly, direct orders (from e.g. hypermarkets) could be individually loaded into NMLUs according to the order (e.g. half shampoo and half washing powder) and then directly be moved towards the outbound area.

Storing areas at the manufacturer site (or at manufactured DC) are currently being filled with products on pallets which in this case will change to NMLUs (at least for the type of products that will be shipped within NMLUs). In this use case, and if not directly ordered from the store, the NMLUs will also serve as the minimum picking quantity until being at the Urban Hub.

5.3.2 Urban Hub

Like mentioned above, the Urban Hub can be either owned by the manufacturer, retailer or other members of a common collaboration model or can be operated by a third-party logistics provider. Urban Hubs are originally located at the edge of the city or within, when using the existing infrastructure such as parking garages that may not be used or are not vacant during e.g. nighttime.

The difference with a regular DC of a retailer is that it is operated by a 3rd party logistics provider that then delivers efficient milk runs within city which can only be achieved by mixing up various retailers. Again, they could also be operated by partners within a collaboration model. This must be evaluated within further work.

As Urban Hubs within this use case also fulfill the role of common (Retailer) DCs, follow up distribution (excluding the Micro Hub approach) works analogically to chapter 5.2.2: The NMLUs will come inbound and unloaded for products to be picked (store-wise) for final distribution to the retailer's stores (business as usual – filling pallets or dollies with products). For final distribution, either regular transport vehicles or NMLUs may be used either way.

Also, picking within NMLUs for serving the role of Micro Hubs is possible. A detailed approach on this case has not been set yet but will be constructed and evaluated within further work.

5.3.3 End Destinations

For such a use case, large stores (and possibly malls) and regular to smaller sized stores will work for final distribution either way as well as the previously mentioned Micro Hubs. In the case that NMLUs are used for final distribution to stores, the transport vehicle will pick up empty NMLUs that are – in the best case – filled with reusables and disposal.

NMLUs serving as Micro Hubs could be used with e.g. Cargo Cruisers and/or other alternative light distribution vehicles (cargo bikes). In that case, there need to be smart loading and unloading zones (also stores are possible), where a collection of NMLUs may be deployed as an innercity depot point for an association of merchants. These could be picked up respectively changed when newer NMLUs are being delivered and then sent back to the Urban Hub.

5.4 Further Approach

The identified use cases are also the starting point for the technical design concept of the NMLUs as they set the general framework and the resulting requirements within all steps of the overall supply chain.

The next step on identifying relevant and beneficial use cases is the further evaluation of actual numbers between the current state of the art and the cases identified. For this, data from the partners and anonymized reference data of recent projects of Fraunhofer IML and Mines ParisTech will be put into a calculation model that comes from a framework developed by Mines ParisTech. Using the knowledge and expertise of the manufacturer P&G, relevant volumes and products that may actually make use of the newly developed NMLUs will be identified.

After relevant and beneficial use cases are proved to function, business cases have to be developed so that all partners within the supply chain will benefit from it. This includes models such as gain sharing and the general question about having a pooling service or if users are buying NMLU devices themselves. Collaboration may influence the point of view drastically as it opens possibilities for business models that may not be achieved if it was without them. All of these questions are to be answered within the next step.

6 NMLU Design concept

This chapter will point out the different NMLU design concepts that came out of the identification of basic requirements and initial solutions that were captured. After that follows the decision-making process which results in the final NMLU design concept. More detailed descriptions of the various steps will be given within the upcoming chapters.

Figure 9 - Overview on NMLU design concepts

6.1 Initial NMLU design concepts

Key requirements are that NMLU must be designed to fit seamlessly in different cargo streams. It must fit in different vehicle types such as trailers, motorcars, kombi's and urban delivery vehicles with high efficiency. A number of X MLU's must fill optimally a 13,6 m trailer, but a row of MLU's must also fit well to the 20,40 or 45 feet see container dimensions (see Annex table 11 ff). A design of a NMLU that would fit in an air cargo ULD (universal loading device) is very beneficial. For city distribution the NMLU's will be compared to units designed in the past such as city box, e.g. Hellmann box or Stadsbox (see chapter 3).

Out of these general basic requirements and throughout workshops between the partners of work package 4, two main systems were identified. On the one hand there is the stand-alone concept, which can be split between the "In-Line" concept and the "Fit-In" concept. Generally, the stand alone concept describes the NMLU as a device that can be treated and handled separately. The Fit-In concept is a resource for packaging load devices which enables loading into an existing container. These are referred to as NMLU(S). The In-Line concept is based on the idea to divide the container into several slices that can all be treated individually and are connected to each other which in the end means, that they will act as the container. The outer dimensions will match a 45 ft. container in width and height. This concept is referred to as (N)MLU.

On the other hand a "Subframe" concept utilizes a subframe on which NMLUs can be placed and fixed, forming a trailer of equivalent transport unit (e.g. a 45 feet container or swap body). The outer dimensions should be in line with given standards.

The different terms NMLU (NMLUS, MLU, MLUSA, NMLUG) that come up within this chapter were chosen so that the different concepts can be distinguished easily and give information about their respective size.

6.1.1 Stand alone

Within the stand-alone concept each NMLU is treated individually. This means that every sub-container can be transported and transshipped without further modification. Therefore, each element is equipped with all the mechanisms that make the NMLU “intelligent”. This includes elements to connect individual NMLUs physically, securing mechanisms, communication equipment and burglar proofing, too.

General idea

Two possible strategies are defined for the new load module, the MLU. One strategy is the idea that the new module must always fit in consisting sea containers, hereafter referred to as MLU. A big advantage of this strategy is, that the MLU fits in the existing modular logistic streams. Disadvantage is that the load efficiency when using euro pallets is very low as the ISO (sea) container has a standard inside width of 2334 mm.

Figure 10 - Overview of “fit-in” NMLU small that fits into a sea container or trailer

The other idea is that a matrix, single or double row, of NMLU's have about the same outer dimensions as the sea containers (2438 mm). So X assembled parts of the new module must achieve the exact dimension and strength of a standard 20 or 40(45) feet container, but also the same handling possibilities. To be able to handle the NMLU's on same way as these containers they must be coupled to each other and have same strength and weight demands as the existing 20 or 40 feet containers. The stand-alone concept is in line with this strategy.

Figure 11 - Overview of the “in-Line” NMLU that is equal to sea container dimension

As mentioned in chapter 4 the NMLU must be dimensioned, that it has a high load efficiency for existing cargo units such as euro pallets, roll container, modulushca boxes.

Figure 12 - NMLU optimally filled with modulushca boxes

The inner dimensions of the floor must be chosen so that a number of euro pallets fit in the height chosen so that at least 2 euro pallets fit in the height. In transitional period UK pallets should be also taken in account. In future developments, the euro pallet might become obsolete but on short term it is not expected. Interfaces on the inner site, in the walls, to put 2 pallets on each other would be worthwhile when they don't reduce the efficient inner volume. A mix of different loading units of must be positioned and secured on the bottom of the NMLU.

Figure 13 - NMLU loaded with different cargo units or a mix

The NMLU must be accessible from at least one side to load and unload. This must be a fast opening door or shutter, that can't be in the way when opened and can be sealed for TIR. Because of the thickness of the bottom a bridge might be necessary to get the cargo units on the bottom.

Figure 14 - MLU in open and closed position

Figure 15 - outer dimensions of stand alone NMLU

Number NMLU's per European trailer shipment: 7 (7 x 1800 = 12.600 mm)

In circumstances that the loading system is not in operation or available the NMLU must be lifted or transported with forklifts. Holes to lift if it up are foreseen.

Figure 16 - holes for forklift (side view of NMLU)

The NMLU must have interfaces to link them to each other. The interfaces are foreseen in the roof and bottom in the front and back side. The interface must be so strong that they can carry a complete line of NMLU's (size 20, 40 or 45 feet), see Figure 17. The connection must be very easy to connect and disconnect. The connection must be opened from bottom side, preferably mechanically driven. The connectors need to be very strong, robust and maintenance free.

Figure 17 - NMLU's forming a 40 feet container

The interfaces to connect the NMLU's to each other on the bottom can be the same interfaces, with the same dimensions, as the corner cubes of the 20 and 40 feet containers with these interfaces the row of NMLU's are mounted on trains and trailers.

The corner cubes must be in every NMLU, because each single NMLU can be lined up in a random way. This gives a lot of extra weight and unused corner cubes.

Figure 18 - Bottom interfaces from the “in-Line” NMLU’s

The bottom of the NMLU must be very flat to make automated loading and unloading systems possible. The bottom on the inside must have interfaces to secure the load in the MLU. Load securing rails will be mounted, interfaces to mount double stock beams are foreseen.

Figure 19 - Corner cubes on a container

Technical risks and boundaries

The challenges in stand-alone “in-Line” and “Fit-In” NMLU design concept are on construction side:

- How to make individual NMLU strong and light weight?
- How to make a connected NMLUs as a single “Load” strong enough?

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- How to realize the connection between the “In-Line” NMLU easy and cost-efficient?
- How to disconnect NMLUs fast and easy?
- How to fit it seamless in automated loading systems?

6.1.2 Subframe

In this concept, an extra subframe is introduced.

General idea

The meaning of the subframe is to deliver the strength of the row of NMLU's when doing the intermodal transshipment. So, the subframe in in “L” shape delivers the base for the NMLU's to make them one unit that is transhipped to train or trailer. For the distribution of each single NMLU, they can be taken directly from the subframe. The subframe can stand on its own feet like a 45 feet container.

The general idea is to split the horizontal movement in two different height levels.

Figure 20 - NMLU subframe concept

The loading and unloading of single NMLU is done at the level of the top of the subframe. The transshipment is done at the level of the bottom from the subframe. In the top of the subframe a bidirectional rolling system (driven or not driven) is made to exchange the NMLU's in different directions, see Figure 15. This makes it possible to combine NMLU's from different origins in one shipment. The NMLU's can be taken out or in in random order. The subframe seems to add extra weight, but because the NMLU can be designed far simpler and because due to the subframe the trailer can be very light weight, there will be a weight reduction in one total shipment. The top height of the subframe on the trailer won't be much more than a standard trailer with integrated roll on / roll off system, so there is no real loss in effective height of the cargo.

When the NMLU's come from the DC, they can be loaded automatically in one row with existing systems. The NMLUs can go on the subframe, on the container chassis or in a normal air cargo trailer with rollerbeds. When they are loaded in the standard air cargo trailer, they can be unloaded from the back, so this is usable for the business case DC to DC transport.

Figure 21 - Loading the subframe at DC

When the NMLU's are loaded on the subframe (with container chassis) they can be horizontally transhipped to trains as can be seen in Figure 22. The subframe is taken from chassis with crane and put on train wagon. This can be done with standard equipment. The trailer is ready to take another subframe or other 40/45 feet container because it has standard interfaces.

Figure 22 - Transshipment of subframe from trailer to train

The System to be able to do this is provided e.g. by Innovatrain Ltd, see below:

Figure 23 - ContainerMover 3000 for 20' to 25' Container up to 18 tons

Figure 24 - ContainerMover 4000 for 20' to 45' Container up to 34 tons (available from beginning of 2018)

Figure 25 - Shifted subframe with MLUs on train

The train wagon is always optimally filled, loaded fast and the subframe can be loaded with NMLU's from different carriers, an optimal case of horizontal collaboration.

Figure 26 - Train filled with NMLU's optimally

The trailer with a fully filled subframe can drop of the subframe of everywhere and put it on his standard feet. The trailer does not need to wait and loose this expensive time.

Figure 27 - Trailer in preparation of unloading of NMLUs at DC

Figure 28 - Trailer setting of subframe filled with MLU's

The subframe can be taken on the train when it is ready or the NMLU's can be swapped in random order to go in local distribution systems.

Figure 29 - Subframe strategy in urban distribution

The shipment can be a mix of NMLU's from different carriers. The subframe offers possibilities to load the MLU's on different DC's from the back or from the side.

Figure 30 - A mix of MLU's from different suppliers or shippers

From business case view the subframe can be owned by shipper, also the MLU's. This case opens up a new business area for the shippers and assets owned Logistics Service Providers.

Figure 31 - Subframe and 8 MLUs as main components of NMLU subframe concept

Based on footprint of 4 euro pallets the number of MLU's per trailer shipment is 8, which is equivalent 32 euro pallets per truck load.

In circumstances that the loading system is not in operation or available the MLU must be lifted or transported with forklifts. Fork lift pockets to up lift are foreseen.

The MLU has interfaces to secure it on the subframe.

Figure 32 - Interfaces in NMLU subframe concept

Technical risks and boundaries

The challenges in Subframe NMLU design concept are on construction side:

- How to make the system light weight, even less or equal to the current related system (45 ft. Container)?
- How realize easy fastening system for NMLUs on Subframe and also Subframe on the Truck or Train?
- How loading and unloading from the back and from the side can be realized technically?

6.2 Decision on NMLU Design Concept

The final decision on the favored NMLU concept has been made within workshop sessions between WP4 partners as well as the LL3 leader. The basis behind that decision was built on the identification of use cases respectively the corresponding overall supply chain (see chapter 5) which led to requirements related to the NMLUs from a holistic view on the supply chain, especially shipping from manufacturing plants to customer DCs/cityhubs including the last-mile aspect, which covers shipments from customer DCs/cityhubs to the stores/consumers.

Once the most promising use cases were set, the pro's and con's of each NMLU concept were individually discussed under the point of view of every stakeholder within the overall supply chain. As a result, the Subframe concept has been chosen for being the most suitable due to the following reasons:

- Easier handling on intermodal shift because of reduced forces onto connected NMLUs
- Possibility to transfer the construction complexity to the subframe and make each NMLU much simpler in construction and in handling and also cost effective
- Possibility of unloading sideways (City-Transport) and backwards (CD and DC) because of no need to load the NMLUs in prescribed sequence and LiFo principle becomes obsolete
- More technical possibilities for automated loading and unloading systems
- Subframe NMLU concept as whole "Load" can be understood legally as a Container, which means 4t additional weight compared to the weight of Trailer

There are further advantages of the subframe concept compared to the Fit-In NMLU concept:

- Possibility of unloading sideways and easier exchange processes of full and empty NMLUs at the end of SC
- Better Volume utilization because auf less packaging in a whole load (With increase number of NMLUs decrease the usable transport volume in the system, subframe is up to 16 % better in volume utilization than Fit-In NMLU)
- Less additional load weight within a fit-in solution due to "double sheathing"

With the subframe concept, the NMLUs can have the same components and features as in the Stand alone version. The NMLUs for the different strategies will be defined in the way that they have about the same inner dimensions. But in the "In-Line" NMLU version, the external length is much higher so that there are less NMLUs per shipment which creates a huge disadvantage. Furthermore a single Subframe NMLU will be lighter and simpler than "In-Line" NMLU because of less construction complexity to reach the needed robustness for transport, warehousing and transshipment.

6.3 Final NMLU Design Concept – NMLU Subframe Concept

The NMLU subframe concept includes two main components: NMLU as an individual sub-container and the subframe (both owned by shipper). The subframe of this NMLU concept is formed by the so-called bottom module, which has the following features:

- Self-supporting, acts as a supporting ground frame for construction
- Complies with the standardized, minimally corresponding profile for guidance, rotating displacement and fixing options for a NMLU
- Provides the possibility of handling forklift trucks on at least the short sides of the NMLU

At the current stage of approach there are the following functionalities of the NMLU, which must be met in terms of logistics requirements:

Subframe

The “L” shape is needed to ensure the safety aspect for the load and the truck driver in case e.g. of emergency braking.

The cubic enhancements are used as table-tracks. These are equipped with rollers. This allows for loading of the subframe from behind. The tracks prevent the NMLUs from moving sideways on the subframe. Using the airsprings of trailer and truck the angle of the subframe is tilted in a way that will allow the NMLU to slide to its destined position. Furthermore, the enhancements can be moved up and down in order to allow the movement of the NMLU on the rollers or to function as guidance.

In the upper position of the rollers, loading from the back is possible and can be automated. Lowering the rollers half way allow for the NMLU to be secured on the subframe with guidance that prevents the NMLU moving sideways. If the rollers are fully lowered the NMLU can be unloaded with for example a forklift truck and damage to the rollers is prevented. For transport, there will be an additional securing mechanism.

Figure 33 - Subframe "L" with splittet Rails

NMLU Walls, Bottom and Doors

To have a lightweight NMLU there can be a composite construction. The main frame of the NMLU will be steel. All laminar areas of the NMLU are areas in which lightweight composites can be used. If those materials turn out not to be sufficiently rigid the walls and roof can also be built as a steel version. In a first prototype plywood will be used for all laminar areas.

The floor of the NMLU is designed in a way that allows a 4way-handling. The openings are designed so that forklift trucks and pallet trucks can handle the NMLU without problems.

To access the NMLU there will be an opening on the wider side. To have a secure door and to reduce the space needed for opening the door the NMLU will utilize a roller shutter. This means that the footprint of the NMLU does not change if the doors are open or shut which makes handling much easier. This is especially important in the use case city distribution. Apart from the stable footprint regardless of the status (opened/closed) the roller shutter is less prone to damaging as there are no protruding elements.

Figure 34 - Subframe NMLU bottom

Fastening system

For securing of the NMLU on the subframe corner cubes will be used. Those corner cubes are located on the four edges of the NMLU and match the system which is used with standard containers. This allows for combined transportation of NMLUs and 20" containers in the future.

The locking mechanism is designed in a way that allows to lower them in order to be able to move the NMLUs on the subframe. Also, it is possible to have the locking mechanism in an electronic version so that individual locks can be opened or closed regarding to the access rights of the user.

Figure 35 - corner cubes to fasten NMLU on Subframe

Dimensions

Right now, the NMLU is designed to take 4 EUR-pallets. In height, it was planned for a double loading height. The outer dimensions of the entire systems (i.e. 8 NMLUs and the subframe) are equivalent to a 45" curtainsider container. The final dimensions of the NMLU will be altered throughout the project. These dimensions will be based on an analysis of the transported amounts of goods.

It is also conceivable to develop two NMLUs for different applications i.e. different dimensions for different goods. For example, a smaller light weight NMLU for city distribution and a larger one for all other steps of the supply chain.

7 Overall Conclusion, ongoing work and outlook

The aim of the Clusters 2.0 project is to leverage the full potential of European Logistics Clusters for an efficient and fully integrated transport system in Europe and demonstrate the scaling effects for the companies collaborating within logistics clusters.

D4.1 includes a comprehensive description of the general requirements of the logistical, transport, transshipment, and storage processes of the NMLU as well as technical requirements from specific use cases (transport from manufacturer to DC and city distribution). The technical requirements also address findings from the related concepts and solutions from the past. In addition, two concepts and first draft designs of the NMLU, describing the current state of the NMLU from the general idea, features to technical restrictions and risks have been developed.

The Subframe NMLU concept is to be discussed as the project proceeds. This concept integrates the substructure into a system element, which not only offers technical advantages but also increases the integration and market acceptance because of a possible integration within the current state. Thus, the substructure and the individual NMLUs form the dimensions of a 45 foot container, allowing individual access to the NMLUs and speed up the wrapping processes by means of wheels and simple fastening mechanisms.

In the course of several workshop rounds, the following points will be discussed in detail up to the realization of the NMLU in D4.3:

- Use Case Evaluation: Data from the partners and anonymized reference data of recent projects will be put into a calculation model that comes from a framework developed by Mines ParisTech. Additionally, the knowledge and expertise of the manufacturer P&G, concerning relevant volumes and products that may actually make use of the newly developed NMLUs will be identified.
- Business Case Development: After relevant and beneficial use cases are validated business cases have to be developed so that all partners within the supply chain will benefit from it. This includes models such as gain sharing and the general question about having a pooling service or if users are buying NMLU devices themselves. Collaboration may influence the point of view drastically as it opens possibilities for business models that may not be achieved if it was without them. All of these questions are to be answered within the next step.
- Technical realization of requirements: The result of this partial work package should be an overview of the technical realization of the selected requirements. For this purpose, the "must-have" criteria are translated into technical solutions and then integrated into an overall concept or the current designs are supplemented accordingly.
- Rapid prototyping of NMLU: In the short term, there will be two or three NMLU prototypes in a simple version (1. Iteration). For these prototypes, a series of tests (Loading and unloading freight, Handling of NMLU at DC and warehouse) in LL3 will be used to learn and finally define a concept.
- Prototyping of NMLU subframe: The preferred subframe concept of the NMLU is to be implemented as a prototype in the mid or long term. Prototype of Subframe with NMLUs will be tested and validated in further LL3 test scenarios to show into a real business context WP4 outputs (see D5.4 Innovative Cluster Handling Technology Scoping Document). When either the subframe concept is implemented and facilitates market entry and market participants are quickly accepting the system, or if the stand-alone

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concept is favored during the prototypes in D4.3, a corresponding market entry strategy will be then developed for the solution and the downstream systems will be designed.

References

- [1] The Consumer Goods Forum, „Modularisation,“ 2016. [Online]. Available: <http://www.theconsumergoodsforum.com/e2e-value-chain-projects/modularisation>. [Zugriff am 25 10 2017].
- [2] MODULUSHCA, „Modular Logistics Units in Shared Co-modal Networks,“ Project Final Reprot, Brussels, 2016.
- [3] GS1 Germany GmbH, „Drogerieartikel sollen in Standard-Transportbox zum Handel,“ press release of 29. March 2017, Köln, 2017.
- [4] ECR Austria, „Standardisierte Abmessungen für Transport- und Lagereinheiten sorgen für mehr Effizienz in der Logistikkette. Diese Standards werden Efficient Unit Loads (EUL) genannt,“ ECR Austria, 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://www.ecr.digital/book/optimierter-warenfluss/eul-empfehlungen/>. [Zugriff am 25 10 2017].
- [5] G. Haubenreißer , J. Neumann und B. Cetinkaya, „Palettenladehöhen in der deutschen Konsumgüterindustrie im Jahr 2013,“ GS1 Germany / Accenture, Köln, 2014.
- [6] IEC 60721-3-2 : 1997, „Classification of environmental conditions – Part 3: Classification of groups of environmental parameters and their severities – Section 2: Transportation,“ German version EN 60721-3-2 :1997, 1997.
- [7] EN 13382:2002, „Flat pallets for materials handling - Principal dimensions,“ German version DIN 13382, 2002.
- [8] A. Vastag, D. Kirsch, A. Brensmann, C. Moll und M. Stockmann, „Potenziale einer Geräuscharmen Nachtlogistik – Ergebnisse und Handlungsempfehlungen des Forschungsprojekts GeNaLog,“ Fraunhofer Verlag, Dortmund, 2017.
- [9] S. Möde, „Urban Retail Logistics - Entwicklung innovativer Technologien und Services für die urbane Handelslogistik (URL) : Laufzeit: vom 01.06.2010 bis 31.12.2013,“ Konsortialbericht zum Verbundprojekt: Leitthema: Urbane Versorgung, Dortmund, 2014.
- [10] S. Stütz und L. Siedlarek, „Potenziale einer innovativen Stadt-Logistik in Bottrop. Ergebnisse eines Forschungsprojekts Innovationcity Logistik Bottrop,“ Fraunhofer Verl, Stuttgart, 2016.
- [11] INRIX 2016 Traffic Scorecard, „Verkehrsstaus verursachen Kosten von 69 Milliarden Euro – allein in Deutschland,“ 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://ap-verlag.de/verkehrsstausverursachenkosten-von-69-milliarden-euro-allein-indeutschland/31311>. [Zugriff am 16 10 2017].

Annexes
Table 10 - Overview of common FMCG transport carriers

Picture	Description
SMALL LOAD CARRIERS	
	<p>Fruit and vegetable crates</p> <p>Fruit and vegetable crates are used throughout Europe in various sizes and designs.</p>
	<p>Meat crates E1 – E4</p> <p>Meat crates are used throughout Europe in various sizes.</p>
	<p>Meat crate E-Performance new</p> <p>The blue meat crates should remove the red ones.</p>
	<p>Aldi-freshbox</p> <p>Supplier of the containers is Walther as well as the intermediate service provider Interseroh.</p>
	<p>DM-folding box</p> <p>Dimensions: 600x400x285 mm Customer branding, Special floor with drain device</p>
	<p>Esprit-folding box</p> <p>Dimensions: 600x400x288/285 mm Height folded: 55-60 mm Sides and floor: closed – Sandwich floor</p>
	<p>Folding container “Utilisys” of bekuplast</p> <p>Development especially for flower bulb exportation. Advantages: easy handling, good ventilation, high volume reduction</p>

	<p>EPS folding box</p> <p>Supplier of the box is the company bekuplast. Due to the volume reduction is the installation height 30 cm.</p>
	<p>Minibox Surplus</p> <p>Reusable folding box with the size 266x171x105 mm. Up to 436 filled boxes fit on one pallet.</p>
<p>PALLETS</p>	
	<p>Euro-pool pallet 800x1200</p> <p>The Euro-pool pallet is a wooden pallet which is accessible from all four sides. It is most commonly used throughout Europe.</p>
	<p>CHEP-euro pallet 800x1200</p> <p>The pallet is used exclusively by CHEP customers in Europe and is designed for the food industry.</p>
	<p>LPR-euro pallet 800x1200</p> <p>LPR-euro pallets are used throughout Europe.</p>
	<p>IPP Logipal E812 800x1200</p> <p>Pooling pallet – mainly deployment in France and Benelux</p>
	<p>Euro 2-pallet 1000x1200</p> <p>The Euro 2-pallet of EPAL is a classic industrial pallet with cross nailed covering boards.</p>

	<p>Euro 3-pallet 1000x1200</p> <p>The Euro 3 pallet is a large euro pallet. The covering boards are nailed along and it has 3 runners.</p>
	<p>CHEP-industrial pallet 1000x1200</p> <p>The CHEP industrial pallet is used throughout Europe. It is the most widely used industrial pallet in Europe.</p>
	<p>IPP Logipal A1210 1000x1200</p> <p>Pooling pallet – mainly deployment in France, Benelux and UK</p>
	<p>Düsseldorfer-half pallet 600x800</p> <p>Most of them are used for the discounters ALDI, LIDL, etc.</p>
	<p>CHEP half-pallet 600x800</p> <p>CHEP half-pallets are used throughout Europe. Mostly in German food distribution.</p>
	<p>LPR half-pallet 600x800</p> <p>The pallets are used in Europe with the dimensions of 600x800 mm.</p>
	<p>Euro H1 800x1200</p> <p>Due to hygiene regulations the fresh meat sector only uses plastic pallets.</p>
	<p>Plastic pallet CR1 800x1200</p> <p>The CR1 from Craemer is characterized by an extremely high load capacity. Static load: 7500 kg dynamic load: 1500 kg</p>

	<p>CHEP plastic pallet 800x1200</p> <p>The CHEP plastic pallet has dimensions of 800x1200x160 mm and a weight of 22 kg. It is accessible from all four sides.</p>
	<p>CHEP ¼ pallet 400x600</p> <p>CHEP half-pallets are used throughout Europe. Mostly in German food distribution.</p>
<p>LARGE LOAD CARRIERS</p>	
	<p>Roller container</p> <p>Roll containers are often used in the classical food trade. Main applications: Picking and delivery of the warehouse as well as the POS</p>
	<p>Dolly</p> <p>Available in various models, essential in the trade</p>

Table 11 - Overview of common EU Swap Bodies

Picture	Description																		
EU SWAP BODYS																			
	C745 Swap Body steel / curtain side / max 18 Europallets <table border="1" style="margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto;"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>outside</th> <th>inside</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>length</td> <td>7.450 m</td> <td>7.300 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>width</td> <td>2.550 m</td> <td>2.470 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>height</td> <td>2.750 m</td> <td>2.525 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>door height</td> <td>2.500 m</td> <td>2.500 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>door width</td> <td>2.440 m</td> <td>2.440 m</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		outside	inside	length	7.450 m	7.300 m	width	2.550 m	2.470 m	height	2.750 m	2.525 m	door height	2.500 m	2.500 m	door width	2.440 m	2.440 m
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	A1370 - 45' Swap body (pallet wide) / max 34 Europallets <table border="1" style="margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto;"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>outside</th> <th>inside</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>length</td> <td>13.716 m</td> <td>13.620 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>width</td> <td>2.550 m</td> <td>2.470 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>height</td> <td>2.725 m</td> <td>2.550 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>door height</td> <td>2.475 m</td> <td>2.475 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>door width</td> <td>2.460 m</td> <td>2.460 m</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		outside	inside	length	13.716 m	13.620 m	width	2.550 m	2.470 m	height	2.725 m	2.550 m	door height	2.475 m	2.475 m	door width	2.460 m	2.460 m
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Table 12 - Overview of common ISO Container

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ISO Container																																			
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Table 13 - Regulation on Trailer outer dimensions by ISO 612-1978

Picture	Description								
Restrictions of the outer dimensions (entire vehicle)									
<p>The diagram shows a side view of a trailer with a red cab and a grey trailer. A horizontal line above the trailer is labeled 'length'. A vertical line on the right side is labeled 'height'. Below the side view is a top-down view of the trailer chassis, with a horizontal line across the width labeled 'width'.</p>	<table border="1" style="margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto;"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th style="text-align: center;">outside¹</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>length</td> <td style="text-align: center;">18.750 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>width</td> <td style="text-align: center;">2.550 m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>height</td> <td style="text-align: center;">4.000 m</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>¹ ISO-Norm 612-1978 ² Internal Dimensions depends on the vehicle design</p>		outside ¹	length	18.750 m	width	2.550 m	height	4.000 m
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length	18.750 m								
width	2.550 m								
height	4.000 m								

Annex 14 – Requirements questionnaire

 Link to full Requirements Questionnaire: <https://goo.gl/forms/OzTib4am9QPvNjT52>

The screenshot shows a Google Form interface. At the top right, there is a teal header bar with a white pencil icon. The main content area is white and contains the following text:

NMLU - Requirements Questionnaire

Dear participant, thank you very much for taking your time to answer the questionnaire. With your answers, we will be able to extract the information provided by you and your use case and merge it together with the other use cases. This will lead to highly relevant information concerning dimensional and technical requirements for the development of our NMLU. Please keep in mind that we focus on FMCG.

Below the text is a progress bar showing approximately 10% completion, followed by the text "Page 1 of 8". To the right of the progress bar is a grey button labeled "NEXT".

At the bottom of the form, there is a small grey speech bubble icon and a line of text: "This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google. Report Abuse - Terms of Service - Additional Terms". Below this is the "Google Forms" logo.

The screenshot shows a Google Form titled "NMLU - Requirements Questionnaire". The form is displayed on a teal background. At the top right, there is a teal header bar with a white pencil icon. Below the title, there is a teal bar with the text "General Information". The form contains three sections: "Name of editor" with a text input field labeled "Your answer"; "Company of editor" with a text input field labeled "Your answer"; and "Use case responsibility" with three radio button options: "Modal Shift", "Warehousing", and "City Distribution". At the bottom of the form, there is a progress bar showing "Page 2 of 8", two buttons labeled "BACK" and "NEXT", and a warning message: "Never submit passwords through Google Forms." Below the form, there is a footer with the text "This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google. Report Abuse - Terms of Service - Additional Terms" and the "Google Forms" logo. A small speech bubble icon is visible in the bottom left corner of the teal background.

NMLU - Requirements Questionnaire

General Information

Name of editor

Your answer

Company of editor

Your answer

Use case responsibility

Modal Shift

Warehousing

City Distribution

Page 2 of 8

BACK NEXT

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Google Forms

NMLU - Requirements Questionnaire

Transportation

This section will ask questions about the transportation requirements of the current system. Please note that we are asking how things are done today.

Within your use case, what load carrier type is mostly being used?

- Container 20 ft
- Container 40 ft
- Container 45 ft
- Trailer
- Vans
- Other: _____

How are the contents of the load carrier mostly handled?

- onto EUR-pallets
- onto industry pallet
-

NMLU - Requirements Questionnaire

Transshipment

Transshipment is divided into two parts. The first part will ask questions about the current shift of load carriers while the second part will address the current situation at warehouses (and depots). Please note that we are asking how things are done today.

Shifting of load carriers

Description: This aspect concerns only the shift of full load carriers (containers). Picking of contents will be asked for under cross docking.

How are load carriers shifted?

- Truck / Truck
- Truck / Train
- Train / Train
- Train / Vessel
- Train / Truck
- Truck / Van
- Other: _____

Depending on shift type, what are the technical requirements for each?

Description: We need to know what happens when shifting. E.g. if a clamp is used, how does it connect to the container, what pressure is applied onto the container, what weight restrictions are there etc. Ideally send blueprints via email to us.

Your answer

NMLU - Requirements Questionnaire

Relevant Process KPIs

In order to be able to compare the current situation with a future NMLU scenario, we would like to ask you for KPIs if it is possible for you to share this information with us.

Shifting of load carriers

Description: In the following, process steps refer to "Goods In", "Picking", and "Goods Out" as a generalized point of view

of deliveries at terminal [vehicles/day]

Process defined as "Goods In"

Your answer _____

of departures from terminal [vehicles/day]

Process defined as "Goods Out"

Your answer _____

of destinations from terminal [# /day]

Description: After transshipment, how many different destinations are targeted?

Your answer _____

Process costs for each process step [EUR/load unit]

e.g. per pallet

Your answer _____

NMLU - Requirements Questionnaire

Future Requirements for a NMLU

At this point, we would like to ask you to leave the point of view of the current situation and focus on the use of the future NMLUs.

For your business case, what are possible/future requirements for an NMLU?

This may also include the optimal number of quantities of contents, accessibility etc.

Your answer

 Page 6 of 8

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The screenshot shows a Google Form titled "NMLU - Requirements Questionnaire". The form is displayed on a light blue background with a teal header. The main content area is white. At the top right of the teal header is a small teal square with a white pencil icon. Below the title, there is a teal bar with the text "Additional Information". Underneath this bar, the text reads "From your point of view, have we forgotten anything?". This is followed by the question "Is there anything you would like to add?". Below the question is a text input field with the placeholder text "Your answer". At the bottom of the form, there is a progress bar showing approximately 70% completion, followed by the text "Page 7 of 8". To the right of the progress bar are two buttons: "BACK" and "NEXT". Below the buttons, there is a small text note: "Never submit passwords through Google Forms." At the bottom of the form, there is a small teal square with a white speech bubble icon. At the bottom of the page, there is a small teal square with a white speech bubble icon.

NMLU - Requirements Questionnaire

Additional Information

From your point of view, have we forgotten anything?

Is there anything you would like to add?

Your answer

Page 7 of 8

BACK NEXT

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Google Forms

NMLU - Requirements Questionnaire

Thank you very much for your time!

If you have any questions and/or files you want to share, contact either

Martin Stockmann
martin.stockmann@iml.fraunhofer.de
Phone: +49 (0) 231 9743 574

or

Michael Koschamvj
michael.koschamvi@iml.fraunhofer.de
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